

1 **HPV E5 control of Pax8-as1.**

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6 The functions of the E5 gene of human papillomavirus remain incompletely defined. Some have described
7 partial transforming potential for E5 but only E6 and E7 are known to induce transformation through
8 inactivation of p53 and Rb1. We used transcriptomics here, measuring total transcription by
9 RNA-sequencing following artificial expression of E5 to identify putative E5 network targets and interaction
10 partners in human cells. We demonstrate here weak activation of *Pax8-as1* by the E5 protein of HPV16
11 and HPV84. The data indicate HPVE5 has partial transforming potential.

12 Citations

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